

Effects of Adjunctive Transferrin on Susceptibility and Emergence of Resistance in Gram-negative Pathogens

Ksenia Ershova³, Brian M. Luna¹, Vladimir Zelman^{1,3}, Brad Spellberg^{1,2}

¹ University of Southern California Keck School of Medicine, Department of Medicine, Los Angeles, CA, USA

² University of Southern California Keck School of Medicine, Department of Molecular Microbiology and Immunology, Los Angeles, CA, USA

³ Skolkovo Institute of Science and Technology (Skoltech), Moscow, Russia

Keywords: *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, antibiotic resistance, transferrin

Introduction

The high speed of antibiotic resistance formation in nosocomial bacteria together with overuse of antibiotics have promoted the current multi-drug resistance crisis. We attempted to decrease the emergence of resistant mutants using a novel combination of antibiotics with recombinant human transferrin (rh-transferrin). We hypothesized that rh-transferrin, which functions by passively starving the bacteria of iron needed for microbial replication [1], would exert less selective pressure as compared to traditional antibiotics. It has been reported in previous studies that transferrin has broad antimicrobial effects *in vitro* against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and fungal pathogens [2].

Project goal

Study the *in vitro* and *in vivo* effect of adjunctive transferrin on susceptibility and emergence of resistance in the Gram-negative pathogens *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Methods

Time kill assays were done using ciprofloxacin or meropenem with and without transferrin. Viability was assessed at 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 24 hours for *A. baumannii* and at 1, 4, and 24 hours for *K. pneumoniae*. The assay was done using either resazurin (cellular metabolic readout) or quantitative culturing. Antibiotic resistant mutants were selected by passaging a high inoculum of bacteria in sub-lethal concentrations of antibiotic for 24 hours or by serial passaging lower inocula of bacteria for 20 days with or without rh-transferrin. Phagocytosis assay with murine macrophages for different bacterial strains after antibiotic exposure with or without transferrin was done. C3HeB/FeJ mice were infected IV and a sub-therapeutic dose of ciprofloxacin (3 mg/kg BID) with and without transferrin (100 mg/kg) was administered. Mice survival was assessed over 7 days.

Results

The time-kill assays for both bacterial species showed mostly no interaction between the antibiotics and rh-transferrin *in vitro* for most strains. Mostly bacteriostatic mode of action defined for transferrin. Mutant selection: for both 24 hours and 20 days passage experiment, more antibiotic resistant mutants were selected for when bacteria were cultured in antibiotic alone vs antibiotic + transferrin. Culturing *A. baumannii* ABO74 in cipro for 15 days leads to increased virulence based on macrophage phagocytosis assay. Transferrin prevents high virulence formation. LD₁₀₀ for all strains in C3HeB/FeJ mice were defined. *In vivo* efficacy experiments will begin soon with combination therapy.

Conclusion

We found that transferrin containing therapeutic regimens suppressed the emergence of resistance *in vitro*, and is promising as an adjunct to antibiotic therapy.

Macrophage assay *A. baumannii* ABO74

Acknowledgement and references

Dr. Brad Spellberg lab: Brian Michael Luna, Travis B. Nielsen, Amber Ulhaq, Jun Yan, Noel Guerrero, Sarah Hsieh, Paul Pantapalangkoor. Los Angeles County + University of Southern California Medical Center, Department of Anesthesiology, Laboratory of Clinical Microbiology, Keck School of Medicine at USC and personally Dr. Rosemary Chia-Jeng She

1. Bruhn KW, Spellberg B. Transferrin-mediated iron sequestration as a novel therapy for bacterial and fungal infections. 2015. *Curr Opin Microbiol*. 27:57-61. PMID: PMC4659759
2. L. Lin, Paul Pantapalangkoor, Brandon Tan, Kevin W. Bruhn, Tiffany Ho, Travis Nielsen, Eric P. Skaar, et al. 2014. "Transferrin Iron Starvation Therapy for Lethal Bacterial and Fungal Infections." *The Journal of Infectious Diseases* 210 (2): 254-64. doi:10.1093/infdis/jiu049.

Skoltech

Skolkovo Institute of Science and Technology

Keck Medical
Center of USC